

Critical Infrastructure Protection Challenges and Best Practices in the Public Administration Sector

A 2030 Outlook

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1. Overview of Critical Infrastructure Resilience

According to the recent publication from the Home Affairs committee [1], the protection of critical infrastructure and the resilience of critical entities operating that infrastructure are vital for modern societies. Without reliable supplies of energy, safe drinking water, health services, banking and financing services, or predictable transportation, among others, our way of life would not be possible. For this reason, the European Commission has long been engaged in supporting the protection of critical infrastructure and the resilience of critical entities against natural and man-made risks. In order to improve the resilience of critical infrastructures, the funding provided by the European

Commission to support such projects amounts to 200M€ in total project cost, with the funds actually offered amounting to 162M€. A total of 25 projects funded between 2017 to 2022 have been included in the analysis. A detailed breakdown of the funding separated by different category is presented in Figure 1. As represented in the chart, Energy, Telecommunication, Water, Smart City, Finance and cross-sectoral areas have attracted a higher proportion of investment in total project cost, while other sectors such as healthcare, e-commerce, transportation and space have received less investment. Despite the high amount of investment that has taken place towards strengthening and increasing the resilience of the critical infrastructure, a recent Directive publication on 'Resilience to Critical Entities' cites a total of 11 sectors that are of priority for Europe, which includes energy, transport, banking,

Figure 1 - Detailed breakdown of the cost category of funding made available to different critical infrastructure sectors [1]

financial market infrastructure, health, drinking water, wastewater, digital infrastructure, public administration, space, and production, processing and distribution of food. Of these key priority areas that have been identified, this paper sets out the challenges and opportunities in strengthening the public administration across Europe.

The public administration sector is among the critical national infrastructure sectors. The body of public administration includes several entities such as state administration bodies, local and regional self-government units, and other legal entities with public powers. The role of public administration is of paramount importance as it brings together the services that are necessary for addressing society's needs by providing essential services for citizens, and it functions based on the organizational structures, processes, public policies, and programs it implements. The role of public administration is particularly important for achieving economic growth, social well-being, and citizen security. At the same time, the quality of the provision of essential public services is an important indicator that reflects the proper functioning of a state. The accelerated pace of social, technological, and economic changes presents additional challenges to public administration. For instance, the shift towards digital governance has expanded the role of public administration, making it a linchpin for ensuring continuity across interconnected systems such as health, energy, and transportation. According to the authors Rehak, Senovsky, and Slivkova [2], critical infrastructure is a complex system designed to facilitate the continuous provision of essential services, and the components of the infrastructure are constantly exposed to the effects of various threats that can generate disruptive events that could lead to the interruption or even stopping of the services provided. In times of uncertainty or crisis caused by anticipated or unpredictable threats, the continuity of essential public services becomes crucial [3]. Examples of such disruptions include ransomware attacks targeting local governments, extreme weather events causing infrastructure failures, and political instability leading to resource constraints.

Administrative resilience according to Sarker [4] is the ability of an administration system to provide appropriate measures to manage uncertainties and bounce back to previous conditions after facing risks, shocks, disasters, and other threats to organizational stability. It also enhances the ability of social systems to remain stable during and after times of adversity. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, administrative resilience was vital in maintaining essential services while adapting policies to new and unforeseen challenges, such as remote working and healthcare surges. One of the key outcomes from the COVID-19 pandemic is the realisation that public administration should be resilient to unforeseen shocks.

Following the investment in the critical infrastructure security and protection, the need for resilience as a holistic concept has gained popularity nowadays. The term resilience refers to the ability of an individual or system to withstand the shocks and stress of social or natural disturbances [5, 6]. For social systems, this ability involves a range of critical administrative structures and capacities aimed at reducing uncertainty and increasing the likelihood of effective response [7, 8]. With respect to disturbances in socio-ecological systems (i.e., natural disasters), administrative resilience is considered an essential capacity for effective organisational responses [9]. Scholars and practitioners of public policy now stress the need for administrative resilience to become a key public policy goal for coping with the risks, shocks, and vulnerabilities associated with natural disasters [10]. Additionally, resilience frameworks increasingly incorporate proactive measures, such as integrating artificial intelligence in disaster risk assessment or developing public-private partnerships to enhance resource availability during crises. While the concept of resilience has been widely promoted for the safety and security of critical infrastructures, the application and adoption of resilience within the public administration has been negligent at best. The scope of the whitepaper is to outline the definition of critical infrastructure within the public administration sector (refer to Section 2) and identify the common threats that are targeted towards the public administration (refer to Section 3).

Subsequently, the need for strengthening resilience in public administration is outlined in Section 4, followed by a survey of resilience frameworks as published in the literature aimed at public administration in Section 5. Conclusion and recommendations are presented in Section 6.

2. Defining Critical Infrastructures in the Public Administration Sector

Critical infrastructure comprises key state assets essential for the continued operation of a nation's core functions. Within the public administration sector, critical infrastructure refers to the entities and services that support governance, societal stability, and the delivery of essential services. This includes state administration bodies, local and regional self-government units, and other legal entities operating in accordance with national law. Public administration oversees vital services across subsectors such as energy, transport, financial services, health, water, the environment, digital infrastructure, food, emergency management, public relations, and legislation. These services are foundational to societal functioning, ensuring the delivery of essential goods, maintaining public order, and facilitating communication and governance. The smooth operation of these services, without public administration, could potentially lead to chaos and disruption in society. By regulating and coordinating these services, public administration plays a crucial role in maintaining stability and promoting the well-being of citizens. For example, public administration ensures the continuity of energy supply during natural disasters, coordinates food and water distribution in emergencies, and maintains legislative operations critical to upholding stability and public trust. Additionally, the sector is pivotal in managing accurate and timely information dissemination during crises, which is crucial for effective communication between authorities and the public.

The reliance of public administration on other essential infrastructures renders it especially susceptible to cascading failures. A disruption in public administration can profoundly affect other industries. A ransomware attack on governmental IT infrastructure may jeopardize financial transactions, hinder healthcare operations, or interfere with emergency response coordination. Failures in the energy sector, such as the 15 million-person-impacting European blackout in 2006 [11] serve as an example of how disruptions can paralyse public administration, causing delays in governance and communication services. The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the critical function of public administration in orchestrating emergency management and resource distribution, emphasising its essential role in crisis management. These cascading effects emphasize the interconnected nature of critical infrastructure: a failure in one domain can ripple across multiple sectors, jeopardizing essential services and public trust.

Incidents like these illustrate the vulnerabilities within public administration systems:

- **Cyberattack on KBC Zagreb, Croatia (2024):** Hackers targeted a major Croatian hospital, disrupting patient records and critical services [12]. Experts highlighted how simultaneous attacks on multiple hospitals could overwhelm public administration's emergency response capabilities [13],
- **Energy Sector Failures in Europe (2006):** The widespread blackout highlighted the vulnerability of public administration to energy disruptions, with cascading effects across communication, governance, and emergency management [14].

Figure 2 - Threat Intelligence Index 2024, page 47. Release date: February 2024 [15]

To address these vulnerabilities, the public administration must prioritize resilience and interconnectedness. Visual tools, such as flow diagrams, can help map cascading effects, illustrating the potential impact of disruptions across critical infrastructures. For instance:

- A cyberattack on public administration could lead to delays in healthcare services, financial systems, and emergency response coordination.
- A natural disaster could simultaneously strain energy supply, water access, and communication networks, compounding the challenges faced by public administration.

Integrating data into resilience planning, like recovery durations from previous cyberattacks or the financial implications of system failures, might assist policymakers in enhancing public administration's capacity to endure and recuperate from crises. By comprehending and mitigating the dependencies and cascading impacts of public administration infrastructure, governments can protect vital services and maintain societal stability despite intricate problems. Government agencies manage daily operations to ensure the efficient delivery of essential public services. This includes establishing protocols for communication and coordination during emergencies, as well as investing in training and resources to ensure a swift response to any disruptions. By prioritizing resilience in their daily operations, governments can better prepare for and mitigate the impacts of unexpected events on public services.

3. Principal Threats to Critical Infrastructure in the Public Administration

Public administration encounters various disruptions, shocks, stressors, and unplanned events. Constant changes in the external environment, such as climate change, new diseases, understaffing, low levels of funding, or insufficient resources, expose public administration to different risks. Security analysis identifies the assets that need protection and the threats they are exposed to, while safety analysis identifies the following as fundamental threats to critical infrastructure:

- Natural disasters,
- Technological accidents,
- Cyber-attacks,
- Criminal activities including terrorist attacks,
- Hybrid threats.

A. Natural disasters

Natural disasters are strong effects of natural phenomena that negatively impact the functionality, structure, and integrity of systems. Basic examples include floods, torrential rain, gales, and heavy snow, which can severely impair the ability of central government to maintain undisrupted services such as transport and emergency responses. Protecting critical infrastructure elements involves improving resistance to these threats.

In September 2023, the city of Derna in Libya experienced catastrophic flooding due to the collapse of two dams after heavy rainfall from Storm Daniel. This disaster resulted in the deaths of thousands and left many more missing. The collapse of the dams and the ensuing floods highlighted significant vulnerabilities in infrastructure maintenance and emergency preparedness within the region. The lack of timely evacuation orders and inadequate disaster response mechanisms exacerbated the crisis, underscoring the critical need for robust infrastructure management and proactive disaster planning in public administration [16].

In September 2024, Hurricane Helene struck western North Carolina, causing severe damage, including the destruction of over 126,000 homes and the loss of at least 100 lives. The disaster overwhelmed local public administration systems, highlighting the critical need for proactive planning and disaster-resilient infrastructure. The deployment of volunteer disaster relief workers at grassroots level exceeded the capacities of FEMA and the local authorities. Churches, shops and even private properties were converted into distribution centres for relief supplies. Volunteers used ATVs and mules to deliver supplies to isolated communities, exemplifying the critical role of community-led initiatives in disaster response [17, 18]. The 2024 flash floods in Spain's Valencia region highlighted the challenges public administration faces in disaster management. Despite warnings from the state weather service and hydrography experts, the regional administration's delayed response in alerting citizens and advising them to stay at home led to criticism. In Spain, regional governments are primarily responsible for disaster management. A lack of coordination and preparedness exposed vulnerabilities in the chain of command during emergencies, highlighting the need for clearer disaster response protocols and improved intergovernmental cooperation [19].

B. Technological accidents

Technological accidents are incidents that have a negative impact on the functionality, structure, and integrity of critical infrastructure due to internal factors like system faults, failures, or unreliability. These issues can lead to uncontrolled degradation and the disruption of essential functions. Ensuring technology reliability and addressing the human factor are key measures in mitigating such risks. Implementing regular maintenance and testing protocols can help identify and address potential system vulnerabilities before they lead to accidents. Additionally, providing thorough training for employees on proper system usage and response protocols can minimise the impact of human error on critical infrastructure.

In May 2021, Poland's Bełchatów Power Plant, Europe's largest lignite-fired facility, experienced a significant outage due to a network failure. This incident led to the automatic shutdown of 10 out of 11 units, resulting in a loss of approximately 3.6 gigawatts of energy. The disruption necessitated emergency electrical imports from neighbouring countries, including Germany, Sweden, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia to stabilize the grid. Human error during the installation of automatic equipment at a power switch caused the outage, highlighting the critical importance of stringent operational protocols and the human factor in maintaining technological reliability within critical infrastructure [20].

C. Cyberattacks

Cyberattacks are targeted activities against the information assets of critical infrastructure, aiming to obtain, modify, or destroy data, or to degrade or destroy the information system. These attacks can severely disrupt critical services, compromise sensitive data, and undermine public trust. Protecting critical infrastructure against such threats requires implementing robust security technologies, including cryptography, reliable secure communication protocols, and advanced threat detection systems. Recent trends indicate that ransomware and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks remain the most prominent threats to public administration systems. According to the ENISA Threat Landscape 2024 Report [21], ransomware accounted for over 50% of reported incidents targeting public and private organizations in the EU in the past year. Threat actors have evolved these attacks into multi-layered extortion schemes, not only demanding ransoms but also threatening to publicly expose sensitive data if demands remain unmet.

As mentioned in ETL 2024 (refer to Figure 3 - Figure 5), the analysis of the top 20 'active' threat actors throughout the reporting period reveals a recurring trend: these actors are predominantly sector-agnostic, with virtually all operating across diverse sectors. The active hacktivist faction continues to favour public administration and transit, which is consistent for 2023. The ENISA report [21] highlights the importance of mitigating such risks.

- Strengthening public-private partnerships for cybersecurity.
- Implementing regular vulnerability assessments.
- Ensuring rapid incident response protocols.

These measures can reduce the impact of cyberattacks and support the resilience of critical infrastructure systems.

Targeted sectors per number of incidents (July 2023 - June 2024)

Figure 3 - Targeted sectors per number of incidents from ENISA Threat assessment landscape [21]

Another figure from ETL 2024 provides more details on the reporting's impact on each sector:

ETL threats per sector

Figure 4 - ETL Threats per sector from ENISA Threat assessment landscape report [21]

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Threat actor per sector

Figure 5 - Threat sector per sector from ENISA Threat Assessment landscape report [21]

D. Criminal activities including terrorist attacks

Criminal activities involve illegal actions aimed at obtaining or destroying elements of critical infrastructure. The goal is often theft, vandalism, or undermining public administration's capacity to operate. Similarly, terrorist attacks target the degradation or destruction of critical infrastructure to enforce political or ideological goals. Protecting such infrastructure requires comprehensive physical security measures.

For example, the coordinated terrorist attacks on public systems in Europe have demonstrated the potential for cascading impacts, such as transport disruptions and public panic, which severely challenge governance systems. The 2016 Brussels bombings targeted the city's airport and metro system, leading to significant casualties and widespread disruption of public transportation. This attack not only caused immediate loss of life but also induced public fear and strained emergency response resources, highlighting the vulnerabilities within critical infrastructure systems [22].

In July 2024, coordinated arson attacks on France's high-speed rail network disrupted major lines, including those connecting Paris with Lille, Bordeaux, and Strasbourg (refer to Figure 6). These attacks occurred just before the opening ceremony of the Paris Olympics, affecting around 800,000 passengers and causing significant travel disruptions. The incidents underscored the susceptibility of transportation infrastructure to deliberate sabotage and the cascading effects such disruptions can have on public order and confidence [23].

Figure 6 – Map of coordinated arson attacks on France's high-speed rail network [23]

These examples illustrate the critical need for robust security measures to protect infrastructure from criminal and terrorist activities, as their compromise can lead to extensive societal and economic consequences.

E. Hybrid threats

Hybrid threats involve coordinated actions that blend cyberattacks with physical sabotage, aiming to disrupt critical infrastructure and create cascading effects across multiple sectors. These multifaceted threats can significantly amplify the scale and impact of disruptions. A notable example of a hybrid threat is the 2015 Ukrainian Power Grid Attack, which combined cyber and physical tactics to disrupt critical infrastructure. In this incident, attackers employed the BlackEnergy malware to infiltrate the IT systems of Ukrainian energy distribution companies. They remotely manipulated Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems to cut power while simultaneously launching a telephone denial-of-service attack to hinder customer communication. This coordinated assault resulted in power outages affecting approximately 230,000 people for several hours [24]. Public administration faces a distinct set of challenges compared to other critical infrastructure sectors. Among these is the responsibility to manage highly sensitive data, including citizen records, financial transactions, and national security information. This makes public administration an attractive target for cybercriminals and malicious actors. Additionally, public administration operates under intense scrutiny from citizens and stakeholders, making the maintenance of public trust essential. The sector also faces unique political pressures; policy decisions, funding allocations, and crisis management can become politicized, further complicating effective operations during emergencies. These various threats to public administration, such as natural disasters and cyberattacks, can have significant impacts across several dimensions as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – Impacts of threats to public administration

Impact	Description
Reputational	Disruptions caused by threats, such as delayed services or data breaches, can erode public trust and damage the reputation of government institutions.
Operational	Threats may interrupt critical public services, such as healthcare, transport, and emergency management, leading to cascading effects across other infrastructures.
Legal	Cyberattacks or operational failures may result in non-compliance with data protection regulations, such as the GDPR, exposing institutions to lawsuits and fines.
Financial	The costs of responding to threats, restoring systems, and addressing vulnerabilities can strain public budgets and divert resources from other critical functions.
Personal	Threats can also endanger public servants and citizens, exposing them to physical harm or identity theft during crises.

The effects of these threats extend beyond immediate disruptions. Public administration's failures in safeguarding infrastructure can lead to political fallout, with opposition parties and public protests questioning the competence of governance. Such incidents can exacerbate social divisions, erode trust in public institutions, and create opportunities for disinformation campaigns that further destabilize public confidence. For example, delays in crisis communication during natural disasters or cyberattacks can fuel misinformation, amplifying public fear and complicating recovery efforts

4. Resilience of Critical Infrastructure in the Public Administration Sector

As the nature of threats and attacks evolve (as cited in Section 3), the role of public administration (and more importantly the role of public administrators) is to constantly adapt and embrace change to evolve and ensure highly qualitative services for citizens and enterprises and develop policies of resilience for other sectors affected by crises. Scholars and practitioners began studying the notion of resilience as they sought ways to enhance the governance process in a system characterized by complexity, constant changes, and new challenges [25, 26, 27]. Countries should survive and develop their ability to cope with potential shocks, such as political instability, economic crises, immigration, climate change, environmental disasters, globalization, demographic changes, or terrorism. Even fast technological development and innovation can be considered factors with a significant impact on societies' normal evolution. In this regard, governments and public institutions play a crucial role by formulating policies that anticipate the impact of potential shocks, prevent their occurrence, assist nations in adapting to ongoing changes, and ultimately recover and evolve after the occurrence of shocks. Resilience frameworks emphasize flexibility, redundancy, and adaptability as core principles for managing these challenges. For instance, adopting proactive risk assessment tools and establishing early warning systems can help public institutions to anticipate disruptions and minimise their impact at the same time.

In this context, a public administration, often characterized by rigidity, should find the necessary tools to fight the unpredictable and absorb constant changes and challenges. Furthermore, public institutions should adapt by embracing change and innovation and evolving while managing to deliver qualitative services for citizens. In this regard, the public administration must strengthen its resilience, a concept that contrasts with the traditional characteristics of public institutions. Based on

rigidity, hierarchy, procedures, formalities, and specific norms, public administration is now confronting the challenge of changing its traditional values. It should become more flexible, adaptable, and, in the end, transformational. In this manner, public administration and its institutions will manage to become resilient and cope with all the unpredictable events affecting the social and economic environment.

The role of resilience strategies

To build resilience, public administration should adopt strategies such as training and education for civil servants, focusing on crisis response, cybersecurity, and adaptive leadership. Additionally, establishing redundant systems and maintaining secure backups ensures operational continuity during disruptions. Public-private partnerships can further enhance resource sharing and mutual aid, fostering a collaborative approach to resilience.

The coronavirus pandemic, for instance, represented a significant shock to public administration, requiring responses to simultaneous crises: the challenges faced by national medical systems and the ensuing economic downturn [28, 29]. Public institutions had to adopt flexible and adaptive policies to mitigate the pandemic's effects while ensuring economic survival. The crisis highlighted the importance of resilience, as public administration had to provide support to vulnerable groups, the medical system, and the workforce while also demonstrating solidarity with other states facing similar challenges.

In times of crisis, public institutions should support all members of society by creating online platforms for communication, providing support for the vulnerable population, and protecting not only those most exposed to risk but also other citizens who can cooperate and help in managing the situation. National economies, regions, or communities will suffer severe consequences if countries fail to prepare their public institutions for crisis management, as they lack the necessary tools to recover or transition to a new state of equilibrium.

5. Resilience Frameworks

Building resilience in public administration requires a shift from traditional stabilization models to frameworks that emphasize flexibility, redundancy, and adaptability. Andreas Duit [30] underscores the need for a paradigm shift in building resilience within public administration, which traditionally relies on rigid bureaucratic structures. He argues that resilient public administration should move toward non-hierarchical networks that cross jurisdictional boundaries, draw on diverse knowledge sources, and engage citizens and stakeholders in decision-making processes. These networks encourage social learning and adaptability by allowing public institutions to experiment with "trial-and-error" policies, enabling them to refine strategies over time. This model of governance shifts away from static hierarchies and instead fosters communication and collaboration across all administrative levels. Public institutions that integrate these principles are better equipped to handle complex, rapidly evolving challenges.

While Duit emphasizes non-hierarchical systems, other scholars highlight that resilience in public administration does not have a one-size-fits-all solution. Context matters greatly, and public institutions must tailor resilience strategies to their unique environments [30]. Public administration must balance two seemingly opposing behaviours: stability and flexibility. Stability ensures routine service delivery, predictability, and efficiency, which are critical for maintaining public trust and confidence. Flexibility, on the other hand, allows institutions to respond quickly to crises and adapt

to unforeseen challenges. The ability to integrate these dual behaviours ensures that public authorities can simultaneously provide reliable services and respond effectively during emergencies [31, 32, 33].

Priorities for public administration reform

Figure 7 - Public governance and administration modernisation [34]

Building resilience may initially appear to demand significant institutional reform, as it requires public administration to challenge deeply embedded norms, procedures, and structures. However, over time, resilience can become part of the institutional routine, reducing the need for constant adaptation. Developing long-term strategies, bureaucratic norms, and procedural frameworks helps institutionalise resilience—creating systems that are stable but capable of evolving when necessary. Stark [35] notes that this process ensures public institutions can sustain efficiency and adaptability, even as challenges evolve. By embedding resilience into their operations, public institutions can meet future challenges with a balanced approach that combines stability and adaptability, ensuring their capacity to serve citizens effectively.

Building resilience in public administration involves adopting frameworks that emphasize adaptability, proactive governance, and collaboration. These frameworks aim to prepare institutions for a range of shocks and stressors, ensuring the continuity of critical infrastructure and public services. The following key elements are essential to creating a resilient public administration:

Risk assessment: Risk assessment is the cornerstone of resilience frameworks, enabling public institutions to identify and mitigate potential threats to critical infrastructure. Regular evaluations of

vulnerabilities—ranging from natural disasters to cyber threats—allow institutions to implement targeted measures to reduce risks. Advanced tools such as predictive analytics and scenario planning enhance risk assessment by providing actionable insights into potential disruptions and their cascading effects.

Capacity building: Resilient public administration relies on robust institutional capacity to adapt and respond effectively to crises. This involves:

- Strengthening organizational structures to withstand shocks.
- Allocating adequate resources to emergency preparedness.
- Establishing clear protocols for crisis management and recovery.

Capacity building entails fostering collaborative networks with stakeholders, including local governments, private sector entities, and international organisations.

Public sector employees' resilience: Various shocks and stresses, such as budgetary cuts, economic crises, political instability, and frequent organizational changes, uniquely affect public administration. Civil servants' resilience is crucial in maintaining institutional stability and efficiency. Resilient civil servants can work effectively under pressure, ensuring continuity of operations despite external and internal disruptions. To build institutional resilience, the focus must first be on human resources. Highly resilient civil servants can help their organisations withstand shocks, such as economic crises or management changes. Furthermore, resilient institutions positively influence community resilience, creating a reciprocal relationship between local communities and public institutions. Understanding and strengthening civil servants' resilience is a fundamental step in fostering institutional resilience.

Training and education for crisis response and cybersecurity: Training programs focused on crisis response and cybersecurity are critical for equipping civil servants with the skills needed to handle emergencies and prevent cyber incidents. These programs should include:

- Simulated crisis scenarios to enhance decision-making.
- Cybersecurity workshops to educate employees on identifying and responding to threats.
- Leadership training to prepare managers for high-pressure situations.

Continued education ensures that public sector employees remain agile and prepared to face evolving threats.

Redundant systems and data backups: Maintaining redundant systems and secure data backups is essential for ensuring operational continuity during disruptions. This includes:

- Backup servers and cloud-based systems to prevent data loss during cyberattacks.
- Alternative communication channels to maintain coordination during crises.
- Ensuring physical redundancies, such as backup power supplies, to prevent operational shutdowns.

Redundancy minimises the risk of catastrophic failures by providing alternative pathways for critical functions.

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): Collaborating with private stakeholders enhances resilience by pooling resources, expertise, and technologies. Public-private partnerships can facilitate the development of:

- Advanced physical security measures.
- Cutting-edge technologies for data protection and operational efficiency.
- Shared emergency response systems.

Such collaborations enable public institutions to access private-sector innovations, ensuring a more comprehensive approach to resilience.

Interagency cooperation: Effective interagency cooperation ensures a unified response to crises by fostering information sharing and resource coordination. Establishing shared platforms for threat intelligence and best practices enables institutions to act swiftly and efficiently during emergencies. Cross-agency collaboration also minimizes duplication of effort and optimizes resource allocation.

Physical security measures: Physical security is a critical component of resilience frameworks, safeguarding infrastructure against criminal activities, terrorism, and natural disasters. Measures include:

- Installing video surveillance systems.
- Deploying security personnel to protect critical sites.
- Reinforcing structural components of facilities to withstand environmental threats.

Cybersecurity as a public good: Cyber threats are a major risk to critical infrastructure, particularly in highly digitised environments. Public institutions must treat cybersecurity as a public good, ensuring the protection of ICT systems that support essential services. Cybersecurity measures should include:

- Strengthening the resilience of information systems to prevent unauthorised access or data breaches.
- Implementing secure communication protocols to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of critical information.
- Conducting regular audits and updates to safeguard against system vulnerabilities.

Role of Cyberspace in CI: Cyberspace serves as the backbone for critical infrastructure operations, enabling information exchange and coordination across ICT networks. However, it is also a domain under constant threat from illegal activities and system failures. To safeguard cyberspace:

- Governments should implement robust cybersecurity laws and frameworks.
- Local governments, as the first tier of crisis management, must prepare for contingencies involving ICT systems.
- Institutions should invest in secure and redundant systems to ensure uninterrupted functionality.

Integrating these elements into resilience frameworks ensures public administration can withstand and recover from disruptions while continuing to deliver essential services. By focusing on risk assessment, capacity building, training, and partnerships, governments can strengthen institutional resilience and safeguard societal stability in an increasingly complex world.

6. Conclusion: How Can We Enhance Resilience in Public Administration

As a conclusion, it is evident from the above analysis that, constant changes are a continuous phenomenon taking place in an ever increasing complex and interconnected world. At the heart of the change are the citizens who need to be protected for maintaining a safe quality of life, that is often provided through the public administration authorities. The radical change in society range from economic and political instability to environmental crises, technological evolution, and emerging cyber threats. To navigate these challenges and continue ensuring citizens' well-being, public institutions must build resilience to effectively manage unforeseen events and adapt to evolving circumstances.

Building resilience in public administration is not a simple task as we have outlined above; it requires a comprehensive and ongoing process that involves addressing both internal and external factors. Internally, public institutions must reform rigid structures and embrace adaptability, enabling them to respond dynamically to crises without compromising operational continuity. Externally, institutions must account for external pressures, including climate change, demographic shifts, and geopolitical conflicts, while maintaining service delivery and fostering public trust. Resilience requires a forward-thinking approach that anticipates risks, reduces vulnerabilities, and ensures the capacity to recover and adapt after a shock occurs. This process of reform demands the active involvement of multiple stakeholders at all levels of governance. National governments, regional authorities, local administrations, civil society, and the private sector must collaborate to create a unified and cohesive strategy for resilience. Public-private partnerships (PPP) play a crucial role by leveraging resources, knowledge, and technology to address critical vulnerabilities. Moreover, the integration of citizens into decision-making processes not only fosters trust but also enhances the effectiveness of resilience measures by incorporating diverse perspectives and needs. Furthermore, resilient public institutions directly influence economic development by creating stable environments that attract investment, encourage innovation, and promote sustainable growth.

In conclusion, advancing resilience in public administration is not merely about managing the present but also about preparing for the future. By embracing resilience as a core principle, public administration can ensure its enduring capacity to serve citizens and support the stability and progress of modern society. Thus far, the observations made in this paper showcase the need for enhancing investment in raising awareness on treating the public administration as a critical infrastructure and the role the public institutions plays in protecting the citizens and the well-being of their citizens at community, regional, and national level. As digital technologies increasingly become pervasive, it is of high importance to ensure the public institutions are well protected against the impeding threats ranging from a multitude of factors. It is crucial that the investment in building resilience within the public institutions should match against the scale of the challenge the public administration authorities are tasked to handle, which is to ensure the well-being of the citizens and protecting the society against all forms of threats. As the next cycle of investment continues to be made in the sector, we recommend public administration should be funded at the same scale as other CIs such as Energy, Transportation, Communication at above 10% of the total allocated value of the overall funding cycle.

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